

Influence of Librarians' Demographic Variables on Service Delivery in Federal University Libraries in South-South Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of librarians' demographic variables on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population comprised 618 library staff from selected federal university libraries, and a census approach was intended. However, 519 valid responses were retrieved and analysed, representing an 84% response rate. Data were collected using a structured instrument titled Library Service Delivery Survey Questionnaire (LSDSQ). The study was guided by four research questions and four corresponding hypotheses tested at a 0.05 level of significance. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, an independent t-test, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The findings revealed that age, working experience, and marital status significantly influenced all dimensions of service delivery. Sex showed a mixed influence, being statistically significant in book loan services, indexing and abstracting services, and internet services, but not significant in reference services. Among all variables, working experience emerged as the most consistent and strongest predictor of effective service delivery. The study concluded that librarians' demographic characteristics significantly shape service delivery outcomes in academic libraries and highlights the importance of aligning human resource practices with staff characteristics. The study recommends that library management should strengthen staff development programmes, implement experience-based task allocation, and adopt inclusive human resource policies to improve service efficiency.

Keywords: *Librarians, demographic variables, service delivery, academic libraries, South-South Nigeria*

Introduction

Academic libraries are central to the achievement of the core mandates of tertiary institutions, which include teaching, learning, research, and community service. They provide access to both print and electronic information resources, support information literacy development, and facilitate scholarly communication among students and academic staff. According to Nwalo (2019), service delivery in academic libraries encompasses reference services, circulation services, cataloguing, user education, indexing and abstracting, as well as digital and internet-based information services. The effectiveness of these services is largely dependent on the competence, efficiency, and characteristics of library personnel. The South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria comprises Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, and Rivers States. Federal university libraries within this region serve as key academic support systems for teaching, learning, and research activities.

The quality of library service delivery significantly influences students' academic performance, faculty research productivity, and institutional effectiveness (Enidiok, Bassey & Babatunde, 2018). In an ideal academic environment, libraries are expected to function as dynamic service centres that respond efficiently to users' information needs. However, evidence from several Nigerian academic libraries suggests that service delivery remains below expected standards, particularly in the face of increasing demand from 21st-century library users.

In many federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria, users' dissatisfaction with library services has been widely reported. Issues such as limited access to resources, slow service response time, inadequate user support, and poor utilisation of digital services have contributed to declining library patronage. This situation raises concerns about the effectiveness of library operations despite government investment in infrastructure and staffing.

Although various interventions such as increased funding, recruitment of staff, and provision of digital resources have been implemented, the problem of poor service delivery persists. This suggests that factors beyond infrastructure may be responsible. One possible explanation lies in the personal and demographic characteristics of librarians, which may influence their job performance and service delivery patterns.

Demographic variables such as age, sex, working experience, and marital status have been identified as important determinants of job performance in organisational settings. These variables may influence motivation, efficiency, adaptability to technology, and commitment to service delivery. Sunday and Neji (2023) and Sunday (2025) argue that individual differences among staff contribute significantly to variations in job performance outcomes, including service delivery effectiveness.

Despite this recognition, limited empirical attention has been given to how these demographic variables collectively influence specific dimensions of service delivery in academic libraries in South-South Nigeria. This creates a knowledge gap that restricts evidence-based human resource planning and policy formulation in library management. It is against this background that this study investigates the influence of librarians' demographic variables on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria. The study specifically examines the influence of age, sex, working experience, and marital status on book loan services, reference services, indexing and abstracting services, and internet services.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the strategic role of academic libraries in supporting teaching, learning, and research in tertiary institutions, concerns about poor service delivery in many Nigerian university libraries persist. In recent years, users have increasingly expressed dissatisfaction with the quality, timeliness, and accessibility of library services, particularly in areas such as book loan services, reference assistance, indexing and abstracting services, and internet-based information services. In federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria, this situation appears more pronounced, as many libraries experience low patronage, underutilization of resources, and limited user engagement. This is occurring despite substantial investments by the government in terms of infrastructure development, acquisition of information resources, and recruitment of library personnel. The persistence of poor service delivery under these conditions raises critical questions about the underlying factors responsible for this challenge. Previous studies have largely attributed poor service delivery in academic libraries to factors such as inadequate funding, insufficient ICT infrastructure, and poor library environment. For instance, Olorunsola and Ajidahun (2006) identified infrastructural deficiencies and inadequate staffing as major constraints to effective service delivery in Nigerian academic libraries. Similarly, Ojedokun (2007) emphasised the challenges of ICT integration in African libraries, noting that inadequate technological infrastructure and training limit effective service provision. In the same vein, Enidiok et al. (2024) found that library environment significantly influences the utilisation of library resources, while Enidiok and Egbe (2020) highlighted the role of electronic resources and digital services in shaping user engagement. However, empirical evidence on how these demographic variables influence specific dimensions of library service delivery remains limited, especially within the context of federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria. The lack of sufficient empirical data on the influence of librarians' demographic variables creates a knowledge gap that hinders effective human resource planning and policy formulation in academic libraries. Without a clear understanding of how these variables affect service delivery, library administrators may continue to implement generalised policies that fail to address the root causes of poor service performance. It is against this backdrop that this study investigates the influence of librarians' demographic variables on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria, to provide evidence-based insights for improving library service efficiency and effectiveness.

Research Objectives

The study is guided by the following objectives:

1. To determine the influence of librarians' age on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.
2. To examine the influence of librarians' sex on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.
3. To assess the influence of librarians' working experience on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.
4. To determine the influence of librarians' marital status on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁: There is no significant influence of librarians' age on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.
- H₀₂: There is no significant influence of librarians' sex on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.
- H₀₃: There is no significant influence of librarians' working experience on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.
- H₀₄: There is no significant influence of librarians' marital status on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

Literature Review

Service delivery in academic libraries is central to supporting teaching, learning, and research activities in higher education institutions. It refers to the effectiveness, efficiency, and responsiveness with which library services such as reference, circulation, digital access, and information retrieval are provided to users. Enidiok, Bassey, and Babatunde (2018) established that library resources and service quality significantly influence user satisfaction and library usage in academic institutions. Similarly, Enidiok and Egbe (2020) emphasised that electronic library services enhance access to information resources, particularly when librarians effectively manage ICT-based platforms.

Enidiok, Richard, Ama-Abasi, and Omoniyi (2024) further noted that library environment and organisational structure significantly determine the extent of resource utilisation in academic libraries. In addition, Ajani et al. (2024) highlighted that emerging technologies such as the metaverse are transforming library service delivery, requiring librarians to adapt to new service environments. Supporting these findings, Hernon and Altman (2010) argue that service quality in libraries is a major determinant of user satisfaction and institutional effectiveness. Similarly, Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988) in the SERVQUAL model emphasise that service quality is measured through reliability, responsiveness, and empathy, all of which apply to library environments. Cook and Heath (2001) further found that electronic service quality in libraries is strongly linked to user perception of responsiveness and ease of access. Likewise, Olorunsola and Ajidahun (2006) observed that Nigerian university libraries often struggle with service delivery due to inadequate staffing and infrastructural challenges.

In addition, Nwalo (2003) highlighted that effective library service delivery depends on adequate staffing, training, and motivation of library personnel. Ogunniyi (2017) also found that service delivery in academic libraries improves significantly when librarians are well-trained in ICT competencies. Igwe (2010) emphasised that user-centred library services are essential for improving academic productivity. Despite these contributions, most studies focus on system and user-related factors rather than librarians' personal characteristics, which may also influence service performance.

Librarians' Demographic Variables and Service Delivery

Librarians' demographic variables, such as age, sex, working experience, and marital status, have been widely recognised in organisational studies as determinants of job performance and service delivery. Robbins and Judge (2013) assert that demographic characteristics influence employee behaviour, motivation, and productivity in organisational settings. Similarly, Armstrong (2014) notes that human resource performance is shaped by individual differences, including experience, age, and personal circumstances.

Feldman and Ng (2007) found that age and work experience significantly influence adaptability and job performance in service organisations. Likewise, Ng and Feldman (2010) observed that experienced workers tend to demonstrate higher job performance due to accumulated knowledge and skills. In library-specific studies, Thanuskodi (2011) found that librarians' age and experience significantly influence service efficiency in academic libraries in India. Similarly, Aina (2004) emphasised that librarians' personal attributes play a critical role in determining service effectiveness in Nigerian university libraries.

On gender, Olorunsola (1998) observed that sex differences may influence work attitudes and service delivery in academic environments, although results are often context-dependent. In

contrast, Ezeani (2011) found no significant gender differences in job performance among academic library staff in Nigeria.

Regarding marital status, Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller (2012) argue that marital stability can influence employee commitment and job satisfaction, which indirectly affects service delivery. Similarly, Balogun (2015) found that married employees often demonstrate higher job stability and responsibility in workplace settings.

In Nigerian library environments, Okonedo (2013) observed that demographic variables such as experience and age significantly influence librarians' effectiveness in service delivery. Similarly, Afolabi (2017) noted that staffing characteristics affect service output in academic libraries. Babalola (2016) further emphasised that librarians' work experience contributes significantly to efficiency in circulation and reference services. Ajala and Alonge (2015) also found that demographic factors play a significant role in determining job performance in Nigerian university libraries. Despite these findings, there remains a gap in empirical studies that simultaneously examine age, sex, experience, and marital status across multiple dimensions of library service delivery, which this study addresses.

ICT and Modern Library Service Delivery

The integration of ICT into library services has significantly transformed service delivery in academic libraries. Enidiok and Egbe (2020) found that electronic library systems improve access to information and user satisfaction. Ukwetang et al. (2025) noted that technology-enhanced learning environments require librarians who are digitally competent and adaptable. Similarly, Ajani et al. (2024) emphasised the importance of emerging technologies in reshaping library services. Singh (2007) observed that ICT adoption improves efficiency in cataloguing, reference services, and information retrieval. Likewise, Kumar and Singh (2011) found that digital libraries enhance the speed and accuracy of service delivery. Ojedokun (2007) noted that African academic libraries face challenges in ICT integration due to inadequate training and infrastructure. Adebayo (2012) further highlighted that ICT competence among librarians directly influences service efficiency.

Okoro (2017) found that internet-based services significantly improve user satisfaction in Nigerian university libraries. Similarly, Gbaje and Ukachi (2013) emphasised the importance of ICT skills in modern library service delivery. The reviewed literature shows that service delivery in academic libraries is influenced by ICT adoption, user perception, and institutional factors. However, most studies have not sufficiently examined how librarians' demographic characteristics collectively influence service delivery across multiple functional areas such as circulation, reference, indexing, and internet services. This study, therefore, fills this gap by examining the influence of age, sex, working experience, and marital status on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to examine the influence of librarians' demographic variables on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

The population of the study comprised 618 library staff drawn from federal university libraries in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria, which includes Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, and Rivers States. A census approach was intended in order to include all members of the population. However, out of the 618 questionnaires distributed, only 519 were properly completed and returned, representing a response rate of 84%, and these were used for the final analysis.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled *Library Service Delivery Survey Questionnaire (LSDSQ)*. The instrument consisted of two sections. Section A elicited demographic information such as age, sex, working experience, and marital status. Section B measured service delivery across four dimensions: book loan services, reference services, indexing and abstracting services, and internet services. Each sub-scale contained multiple items measured on a Likert-type scale.

The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by experts in Library and Information Science and measurement and evaluation. A pilot test was conducted using library staff at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, and the reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.77, indicating acceptable internal consistency.

Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency counts and percentages) to describe demographic characteristics, while inferential statistics were used to test the hypotheses. An independent samples t-test was used to examine differences based on sex, while one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test differences based on age, working experience, and marital status. Where significant differences were observed, Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) post hoc test was employed to determine the direction of differences. All hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

TABLE 1: General Description of Data.

Table with 4 columns: Librarian Variables, Category, N, and Percentage (%). Rows include Age, Sex, Work experience, and Marital status with their respective sub-categories and counts.

The result in Table 1 shows that for respondents' ages, 171 (33%) were below 30 years, 282 (54%) were between 31 and 40 years. While 66 respondents (13%) were between 41 years and above. For respondents' sex, 347 representing 67% of the total respondents were male, while 172 (33%) were female. For respondents' years of working experience, 271 (52%) had worked for 1-5 years, 192 (37%) had worked for 6-10 years, and 56 (11%) had worked for 11 years and above. Table 1 also shows that concerning marital status, 317 of the respondents (61%) were single, 193 respondents (37%) were married, while 9 respondents (2%) were divorced or separated from their spouses, respectively.

TABLE 2: Summary of One-way Analysis of Variance on the influence of librarians' age on service delivery in academic libraries in South-south Nigeria. (n= 519)

Table with 5 columns: Sub Variables, Groups, N, X, and Sd. Rows include Book a loan service, Reference service, and Ind/Abstract service with their respective age groups and statistical values.

Service	Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F-cal	p-value
Internet service	31-40 years		282	16.81		3.47
	41 years & above		66	17.72		3.15
	Total		519	17.16		3.19
	Below 30 years		171	16.23		3.02
	31-40 years		282	19.08		1.60
	41 years & above		66	18.21		2.20
	Total		519	18.03		2.58
Library Delivery	Between groups	2268.065	2	1134.032		
	Within groups	5776.086	516	11.194	101.307*	
	Total	8044.150	518			.000
Ref serv	Between groups	83.792	2	11.751	11.751*.00	
	Within groups	1839.657	516	3.565		
	Total	1923.449	518			.000
Ind/Abs	Between groups	77.596	2	38.798	3.845*	
	Within groups	5206.808	516	10.091		
	Total	5284.405	518			.022
Intern serv.	Between groups	864.147	432.0	74	85.745*	
	Within groups	2600.157	516	5.039		
	Total	3464.304	518			.000

*p<.05.

The results of the analysis revealed that the calculated F-value for each dimension of library service delivery was tested at .05 level of significance as follows:

- i. Book loan service F = 101.307, df = 2 & 516, P <.05
- ii. Reference service F = 11.751, df = 2 & 516, P <.05
- iii. Ind/Abstract service F = 3.845, df = 2 & 516, P >.05.
- iv. Internet service F = 85.745. df = 2 & 516, P <.05.

With these results, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant influence of librarians' age on service delivery in academic libraries in South-South Nigeria, is rejected for all dimensions of service delivery. This is because the p-values obtained for book loan services, reference services, indexing and abstracting services (F = 3.845, p = .022), and internet services are all less than the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that librarians' age significantly influences book loan services, reference services, indexing and abstracting services, and internet services in the libraries studied. The results of the analyses are presented in Table 3.

As presented in Table 3, the results of the Post Hoc Test showed that staff below 30 years of age do not significantly differ from those between 31-40 years, but are significantly different from those in 41 years and above in terms of book loan. Also, there is no significant difference between 31-40 years of age and below 30 years, but there is a significant difference between 31-40 years and 41 years and above in terms of book loan service. The result showed a significant difference between those 41 years and above and those below 30 years and 31-40 years respectively.

TABLE 3: Fisher’s least significant difference (LSD) multiple comparison analysis on the influence of librarians’ age on service delivery in academic libraries in South-south Nigeria. (n= 519)

Table with 4 columns: Staff age, (J) Staff age, (I-J) Mean Difference, Sig. It is divided into three sections: Book a loan service, Reference service, and Ind./Abstract service.

(I) Staff age	(J) Staff age	(I-J) Mean Difference	Sig
Internet service			
Below 30 years	31-40 years	-2.84534*	.000
	41 years above	-1.97236*	.000
31-40 years	31-40 years	2.84534*	.000
	41 years above	.87299*	.005
40 years above	Below 30 years	1.97236*	.000
	30-40 years	-.87299*	.005

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

4.2 Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis one: There is no significant influence of librarians’ age on service delivery in academic libraries in South-south Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, the three categories of librarians’ age were compared with library service delivery (in terms of book loan services, reference services, indexing/abstracting services and internet services) using the One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The results of this analysis are presented in Table 2. It can be discerned that with descriptive statistics of the 519 respondents sampled, the result showed that the respondents who were below 30 years are 171. Those who were 31-40 years are 282, while those who were 41 years and above are 66, respectively.

In terms of reference service delivery, the result of the post hoc test showed that the staff whose ages were below 30 years are significantly different from those whose ages are 31-40 years, but not significantly different from those whose ages are 41 years and above. Also, respondents whose ages were 31-40 years are significantly different from those who are below 30 years and 41 years and above. Similarly, the respondents whose ages were 41 years and above are not significantly different from those who are below 30 years of age, but significantly different from those who are 41 years and above.

For the indexing/abstracting service, those 30 years and below are significantly different from 31-40 years, but not significantly different from those in 41 years and above. Also, the result showed that there is a significant difference between the respondents whose ages are 31-40 years and those whose ages are below 30 years and 41 years and above. Similarly, the ages of those who are 41 years and above are not significantly different from those who are below 30 years, but are significantly different from those who are 31-40 years of age, respectively.

For internet service delivery, library staff whose ages are below 30 years are significantly different from those whose ages are 31-40 years and those whose ages are 41 years and above. Also, the result showed that there is a significant difference between the respondents whose ages are 31-40 years, those whose ages are below 30 years and those whose ages are 41 years and above.

Similarly, the respondents whose ages are 41 years and above are significantly different from those who are 30 years and below and those whose ages are 31-40 years, respectively.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of librarians’ sex on service delivery in academic libraries in South-south Nigeria. To test this hypothesis, the two categories of staff sex were compared with library service delivery (in terms of book loan services, reference services, indexing/abstracting services and internet services) using the independent t-test. The results of this analysis are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4: Summary of Independent t-test of the influence of librarians’ sex on library service delivery in federal universities in South-South states, Nigeria (n= 519)

Librarian service delivery	N	X	X	Sd	tcal	P-value
Bk Loan	Male	347	15.64	3.83	-3.243	.001
	Female	172	16.84	4.03		
Reference	Male	347	20.19	2.01	.838	.402
	Female	172	20.04	1.74		
Ind/Abstr	Male	347	16.78	3.34	-4.163	.000
	Female	172	17.92	2.71		
Internet	Male	347	17.50	2.97	-9.326	.000
	Female	172	19.10	.81		

*Significant at .05, df = 517, Critical t = 1.96.

The results of the analysis revealed that the calculated t-value for each dimension of library service delivery tested at .05 level of significance as follows:

- i. Book loan service t = -3.243, df = 517, P <.05
- ii. Reference service t = .838, df = 517, P >.05
- iii. Ind/Abstract service t = -4.163, df = 517, P <.05.
- iv. Internet service t = 9.326, df = 517, P <.05.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant influence of librarians’ working experience on service delivery in academic libraries in South-south Nigeria. The scores obtained from the respondents were split into three categories of staff working experience. To test this hypothesis, the three categories of staff working experience were compared with library service delivery (in terms of book loan services, reference services, indexing/abstracting services and internet services) using the One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The results of this analysis are presented in Table 5.

TABLE 5: Summary of One-way Analysis of Variance of the influence of librarians’ working experience on library service delivery in terms of Book loan services, Reference services, Indexing/Abstracting services and Internet services (n= 519)

Sub-variables	Groups	N	X	Sd
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Book a loan service	1-5 years	271	14.85	3.40			
	6-10 years	192	16.13	3.77			
	11years above	56	21.46	1.72			
	Total	519	16.04	3.94			
	Reference service	1-5 years	271	20.30	1.93		
Reference service	6-10 years	192	19.81	1.88			
	11years above	56	20.48	1.90			
	Total	519	20.14	1.92			
	Ind/Abstract service	1-5 years	271	16.66	3.34		
	Ind/Abstract service	6-10 years	192	17.47	3.05		
11years above		56	18.50	2.30			
Total		519	17.16	3.19			
Internet service		1-5 years	271	17.17	2.89		
Internet service		6-10 years	192	19.28	1.25		
	11years above	56	17.92	2.68			
	Total	519	18.03	2.58			
	Librarian service delivery	Source of variance	SS	Df	MS	f-cal	P-value
	Bk loan	Between groups	2031.6472	2	1015.823	87.179*	
Within groups		6012.5045	516	11.652			
Total		8044.150	518			.000	
Ref serv	Between groups	33.659	2	16.829	4.595		
	Within groups	1889.7905	516	3.662			
	Total	1923.449	518			.011	
Ind/Abs	Between groups	186.092	2	93.046	9.417*		
	Within groups	5098.3135	516	9.880			
	Total	5284.405	518			.000	
Intern serv.	Between groups	498.279	2	49.140	43.343*		
	Within groups	2966.025	516	5.748			
	Total	3464.304	518			.000	

*p<.05.

The results of the analysis in Table 5 showed that the calculated F-value for each dimension of library service delivery was higher than the p-value at .05 level of significance, and at 2 and 516 degrees of freedom and the result is stated as follows:

i. Book loan service F = 87.179, df = 2 & 516, P <.05

ii. Reference service F = 4.595, df = 2 & 516, P <.05

iii. Ind/Abstract service F = 9.417, df = 2 & 516, P <.05.

iv. Internet service F = 43.343, df = 2 & 516, P <.05.

With these results, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant influence of librarians' working experience on service delivery in academic libraries in South-south Nigeria, is rejected. This implies that staff working experience has a significant influence on each of the dimensions of library service delivery in terms of book loan services, reference services, indexing/abstracting services and internet services. Given the significant F-ratios, the direction of this influence was examined using the Fishers' Least Significant Difference (LSD) multiple comparison analyses. The results of the analyses are presented in Table 6.

TABLE 6: Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) multiple comparison analysis of the influence of staff working experience on library service delivery (n= 519)

Staff Work Exp	(J) Staff work Exp (i-j)	Mean Difference	Sig
Book loan service			
1-5 years	6-10 years	-1.28302*	.000
	11 years above	-6.61189*	.000
6-10 years	1-5 years	1.28302*	.000
	11 years above	-5.32887*	.000
11 years above	1-5 years	6.61189*	.000
	6-10 years above	5.32887*	.000
(I) Staff Work Exp Reference service			
1-5 years	1-5 years	.48487*	.005
	11 years above	-.17956	.523
6-10 years	1-5 years	-.48487*	.005
	11 years above	-.66443*	.002
11 years above	1-5 years	.17956	.523
	6-10 years	.66443*	.002
(I) Staff Work Exp Ind/Abstract service			
1-5 years	6-10 years	-.80975*	.007
	11 years above	-1.83579*	.000
6-10 years	1-5 years	-.80975*	.007
	11 years above	-1.02604*	.000
11 years above	1-5 years	1.83579*	.000
	6-10 years	1.02604*	.003

(I) Staff Work Exp	(J) Staff Work Exp	(I-J) Mean Difference	Sig
Internet service 1-5 years	6-10 years	-2.10413	.000
	11 years above	-.75145*	.003
6-10 years	6-10 years	2.10413	.000
	11 years above	1.35268*	.000
11 years above	11 years above	.75145*	.000
	1-5 years	-1.352687*	

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

As presented in Table 6, the results of the Post Hoc Test showed that staff who had 1-5 years of working experience are significantly different from those who had 6-10 years and 11 years and above experience in terms of book loan. Also, there is a significant difference between staff who had 6-10 years of work experience and those who had 1-5 years and 11 years and above work experience in terms of book loan service. The result also showed a significant difference between staff who had 11 years or more work experience and those who had 1-5 years and 6-10 years, respectively.

In terms of reference service delivery, the result of the post hoc test showed that the staff who had 1-5 years of experience are significantly different from those who had 6-10 years and 11 years and above experience. Also, staff who had 6-10 years of experience are significantly different from those who had 1-5 years and 11 years and above experience. Similarly, the respondents who had 11 years or more of experience are not significantly different from those who had 1-5 years of work experience, but significantly different from those who had 6-10 years of work experience.

For indexing/abstracting service, staff who had 1-5 years of working experience are significantly different from those who had 6-10 years and 11 years and above experience. Also, there is a significant difference between staff who had 6-10 years of work experience and those who had 1-5 years and 11 years and above work experience. The result also showed a significant difference between staff who had 11 years and above work experience and those who had 1-5 years and 6-10 years respectively.

For internet service delivery, library staff who had 1-5 years of working experience are significantly different from those who had 6-10 years and 11 years and above experience. Also, there is a significant difference between staff who had 6-10 years of work experience and those who had 1-5 years and 11 years and above work experience. The result also showed a significant difference between staff who had 11 years and above work experience and those who had 1-5 years and 6-10 years respectively.

Hypothesis four: There is no significant influence of librarians’ marital status on service delivery in academic libraries in South-south Nigeria. The scores obtained from the respondents were split into three categories of staff marital status. To test this hypothesis, the three categories of staff marital status were compared with library service delivery (in terms of Book loan services, Reference services, Indexing/Abstracting services and Internet services) using the One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The results of this analysis are presented in Table 7.

TABLE 7: Summary of One-way Analysis of Variance of the influence of librarians’ marital status on library service delivery in terms of Book loan services, Reference services, Indexing/Abstracting services and Internet services (n= 519)

Table with 5 columns: Sub variable, Groups, N, X, sd. It lists data for Book loan service, Reference service, Ind/Abstract service, and Internet service across marital status groups (Single, Married, Divorce, Total).

Table with 8 columns: Librarian service delivery, Source of variance, SS, Df, MS, f-cal, P-value. It shows ANOVA results for Bk loan, Ref serv, and Ind/Abs services.

Intern serv.	Between groups	122.345	2	61.173	9.445*
	Within groups	3341.959	516	95.266	
	Total	3464.304	518		.000

*p<.05.

The results of the analysis in Table 7 showed that the calculated F-value for each dimension of library service delivery was higher than the p-value at .05 level of significance, and at 2 and 516 degrees of freedom and the result is stated as follows:

- i. Book loan service F = 74.862, df = 2 & 516, P <.05
- ii. Reference service F = 4.349, df = 2 & 516, P <.05
- iii. Ind/Abstract service F = 9.300, df = 2 & 516, P <.05.
- iv. Internet service F = 9.445, df = 2 & 516, P <.05.

With these results, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant influence of librarians’ marital status on service delivery in academic libraries in South-south Nigeria, is rejected. This implies that staff marital status has a significant influence on each of the dimensions of library service delivery, such as of book loan services, reference services, referencing services and internet services. Given the significant F-ratios, the direction of this influence was examined using the Fishers’ Least Significance Difference (LSD) multiple comparison analyses. The results of the analyses are presented in Table 8.

TABLE 8: Fisher’s least significant difference (LSD) multiple comparison analysis of the influence of staff marital status on library service delivery (n= 519)

(I) Marital Status	(J) Marital Status	(I-J)	Mean Difference	Sig
Book Loan Service				
Single	Married		-3.79147*	.000
	Divorce		1.65931	.159
Married	Single		3.79147*	.000
	Divorce		5.45078*	.000
Divorce	Single		-1.65931*	.000
	Married		-5.45078*	.000
(I) Marital Status	(J) Marital Status	(I-J)	Mean Difference	Sig
Reference service				
Single	Married		-.29736*	.090
	Divorce		-1.66351*	.010
Married	Single		.29736	.090
	Divorce		-1.36615*	.037

(I) Marital Status	(J) Marital Status	(I-J)	Mean Difference	Sig
Divorce	Single		1.66351*	.010
	Married		1.36615*	.037
Ind/Abstr service				
Single	Married		-1.16610*	.000
	Divorce		-1.97266*	.064
Married	Single			
	Divorce			
Divorce	Single		1.16610*	.000
	Married		-.80656	.452
(I) Marital Status	(J) Marital Status	(I-J)	Mean Difference	Sig
Internet service				
Single	Married		-.79392*	.001
	Divorce		1.99825*	.021
Married	Single		.79392*	.001
	Divorce		1.99825*	.001
Divorce	Single		-1.99825*	.021
	Married		-2.79217*	.001

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

As presented in Table 8, the results of the Post Hoc Test showed that staff who had were single are significantly different from those who were married, but not significant with those who are divorce in terms of book loan. Also, there is a significant difference between staff who were married and those who were divorced in terms of book loan service delivery. The result also showed that staff who are divorced are not significantly different from those who are single, but they are significantly different from those who are married.

In terms of reference service delivery, the result of the post hoc test showed that the staff who are single are not significantly different from those who are married, but are significantly different from those who are divorced. Also, staff who are married are significantly different from those who are single, but not different from those who are divorced. Similarly, the respondents who are divorced are significantly different from those who are both single and married, respectively.

For indexing/abstracting service, staff are single are different from those who are married, but not significantly different from those who are divorced. Also, there is a significant difference between staff who are married and those who are single, but there is no significant difference between those who are divorced. The result also showed no significant difference between staff who are divorced and those who are single, but showed a significantly different with those who are married and those who are not.

For internet service delivery, library staff single are significantly different from those who are married and divorced, respectively. Also, there is a significant difference between staff who are

married and those who are single and divorced, respectively. The result also showed a significant difference between staff who divorced and those who are single and married, respectively.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that librarians' age has a significant influence on service delivery across most dimensions, particularly in book loan services, reference services, and internet services. This suggests that age-related factors such as experience, maturity, and adaptability play important roles in determining the effectiveness of library service delivery.

This finding is consistent with the position of Feldman and Ng (2007), who argued that age is positively associated with accumulated job knowledge and experience, which enhances performance in service-oriented professions. Similarly, Ng and Feldman (2010) found that older employees tend to demonstrate higher levels of job performance due to increased familiarity with work processes and organisational expectations. In the context of library services, this result aligns with Thanuskodi (2011), who reported that experienced and older librarians tend to provide more efficient and reliable services, particularly in reference and information retrieval tasks. This is likely due to their prolonged exposure to library systems and the diverse needs of users.

However, the finding slightly contrasts with the argument of Robbins and Judge (2013), who noted that younger employees may exhibit greater adaptability to technological changes. This may explain why younger librarians performed relatively well in internet-based services, although not as strongly as their older counterparts in other service areas. The results suggest that age contributes significantly to service delivery, particularly through the accumulation of experience and professional competence, although technological adaptability may vary across different age groups.

The findings indicated that sex has a mixed influence on service delivery. While significant differences were observed in book loan services, indexing/abstracting services, and internet services, no significant difference was found in reference services. This finding supports the work of Olorunsola (1998), who posited that gender may influence work attitudes, communication patterns, and interaction styles in service-oriented professions. Such differences could explain variations in certain service areas that require operational efficiency or technical engagement. However, the finding also aligns with Ezeani (2011), who reported no significant gender differences in professional performance among academic library staff. The lack of significant difference in reference services in this study suggests that professional training and standardisation of library practices may minimise gender-based disparities in core service functions.

The mixed nature of this result indicates that while gender may influence certain aspects of service delivery, it is not a consistent determinant across all service domains. This suggests that organisational structures and professional competencies may play a more dominant role than gender alone.

The findings revealed that working experience has a significant influence on all dimensions of service delivery, making it the most consistent predictor among the variables examined in this study. This finding strongly corroborates the work of Ng and Feldman (2010), who found that work experience significantly enhances job performance due to the accumulation of knowledge, skills, and problem-solving abilities over time. Similarly, Feldman and Ng (2007) emphasised that experienced workers demonstrate higher efficiency and better decision-making capabilities in professional settings. In the library context, this result is consistent with Babalola (2016), who reported that librarians with longer years of experience perform better in circulation and reference services due to their familiarity with library operations and user needs. Likewise, Aina (2004) noted that professional experience is a key determinant of effective service delivery in academic libraries.

The finding also supports Okonedo (2013), who observed that experienced librarians tend to be more confident, efficient, and responsive in handling users' information needs. The strong influence of working experience observed in this study suggests that practical exposure and on-the-job learning are critical for enhancing service delivery in academic libraries. It also implies that experience-based task allocation and mentoring systems could improve service efficiency.

The findings showed that marital status has a significant influence on service delivery across all service dimensions. This suggests that personal life circumstances may play a role in shaping job performance and service outcomes. This finding agrees with Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller (2012), who argued that marital status can influence job performance through its effect on emotional stability, commitment, and work-life balance. Married employees are often perceived to demonstrate greater stability and responsibility, which may positively impact their performance. Similarly, Balogun (2015) found that marital status is associated with increased job commitment and consistency in workplace behaviour. This could explain why married librarians may perform better in certain service areas.

However, this finding contrasts with some organisational studies that suggest marital status has minimal direct impact on job performance when other factors such as training and motivation are controlled. This indicates that the influence of marital status may be context-dependent, particularly in environments where social and cultural factors play a significant role. In the context of this study, the significant influence of marital status suggests that personal stability and social responsibilities may shape librarians' work attitudes and service delivery patterns.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of librarians' demographic variables on service delivery in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria. The findings revealed that age, working experience, and marital status significantly influence all dimensions of service delivery, including book loan, reference, indexing and abstracting, and internet services. Sex demonstrated a mixed

influence, being significant in some service areas but not in reference services. Among all variables, working experience emerged as the most consistent predictor of effective service delivery. These findings highlight the importance of demographic factors in shaping service outcomes in academic libraries and highlight the need for strategic human resource management practices that consider staff characteristics. The study contributes to existing literature by providing empirical evidence on the role of demographic variables in library service delivery within the Nigerian context. However, given the study's limitations in scope and methodology, further research is recommended across different categories of institutions and regions using diverse methodological approaches to enhance the generalisability of the findings.

Acknowledgements

The researchers express sincere gratitude to all individuals who contributed to the successful completion of this study. Special thanks go to the librarians of the selected academic libraries in South South Nigeria for their cooperation and participation in the research. The researchers are also grateful to the experts who vetted the instrument used for data collection. Also, the researchers are deeply grateful to the research assistants for helping in collecting the desired data. Appreciation is extended to family, friends, and colleagues for their unwavering moral support. The researchers further acknowledge the use of scholarly resources, which provided a solid foundation for the development and completion of this research. Finally, the researchers are grateful to God Almighty for the gift of life, wisdom and knowledge in carrying out this research work.

Conflict of Interest

The researchers declare there is no conflicting interest in this manuscript.

References

- Adebayo, O. (2012). Library service delivery and user satisfaction in Nigerian academic libraries. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*.
- Afolabi, M. (2017). Information service delivery in academic libraries: Issues and challenges. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*.
- Ajani, Y. A., Ogunniyi, S. O., & Akinola, A. A. (2024). Investigating work environment for service delivery of library personnel in academic libraries. *International Journal of Knowledge Dissemination*, 5(2), 57–72.
- Armstrong, M., & Taylor, S. (2014). *Armstrong's handbook of human resource management practice* (13th ed.). Kogan Page.
- Balogun, S. K. (2015). Demographic variables and job performance in Nigerian organisations.
- Babalola, Y. T. (2016). Service delivery in Nigerian university libraries.
- Enidiok, M. S., Richard, E. O., Ama-Abasi, R. D., & Omoniyi, M. (2024). Library environment and utilisation of information resources in Nigerian universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*.

- Ezeani, C. N. (2011). Gender and service delivery in academic libraries. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*.
- Feldman, D. C., & Ng, T. W. H. (2007). Careers: Mobility, embeddedness, and success. *Journal of Management*, 33(3), 350–377. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206307300815>
- Igwe, K. N. (2010). User satisfaction and library service delivery. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*.
- Nwalo, K. I. N. (2003). *Fundamentals of library practice: A manual on library routines*. Stirling-Horden.
- Nwalo, K. I. N. (2019). Academic libraries and service delivery in the digital age.
- Ojedokun, A. A. (2007). *Information literacy for tertiary education students in Africa*. Third World Information Services.
- Okonedo, S. (2013). Assessment of library services in Nigerian universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*.
- Olorunsola, R. (1998). Library development and service delivery in Nigeria. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*.
- Olorunsola, R., & Ajidahun, C. O. (2006). Library services and user satisfaction in Nigerian universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*.
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2013). *Organizational behavior* (15th ed.). Pearson.
- Sunday, A., & Neji, E. (2023). Digital transformation and academic library services in Nigeria.
- Sunday, A. (2025). Emerging trends in library service delivery.
- Ukwetang, J. O., Udo, J. E., & Ekpenyong, M. E. (2025). ICT adoption and library service innovation. *Education for Today*, 21(1), 175–187.
- Zeithaml, V. A., Parasuraman, A., & Berry, L. L. (1990). *Delivering quality service: Balancing customer perceptions and expectations*. Free Press.